

CURRENT MEDICINAL APPLICATIONS OF HERBS IN HAIR COSMETICS: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Hair care is fundamental for personal grooming, involving various methods and products to maintain hair health. The utilization of herbal extracts and plant-based ingredients in hair care products has gained momentum recently due to their perceived effectiveness and the growing preference for natural solutions among consumers. This overview explores the importance of hair care routines and the role of effective products. It also represents the current medicinal applications of herbs in hair care products, emphasizing their therapeutic benefits and the scientific evidence backing their usage. Various herb medicines, including aloe vera, bhringraj, shikakai, fenugreek, ginseng etc., are examined for their roles in stimulating hair growth, enhancing scalp health, preventing hair loss, and improving overall hair problems. It also discusses recent advancements, including innovative formulations, eco-friendly ingredients.

KEY WORDS

Herbal Cosmetics, Natural herbs, Hair Care, Oil, Shampoo, Medicinal.

INTRODUCTION

Hair is one of the characteristics features of mammals and has various functions such as protection against external factors i.e., heat, cold, etc. Hair is one of the important parts of body considered to be protective appendages on the body and accessory structure of the integument along with sebaceous gland and sweat gland. (1) The basic part of the hair is bulb, root and shaft. (2) Hair fall, dandruff, lice, split end, grey hair, are some of the well-known problems related to hair. (3) A piece of hair looks simply but it is one of the most complicated structures in body. Hair is made up of two structures i.e., the hair follicle is where hair begins to grow and where it is held in place. It is a stocking-like structure that starts in the epidermis. It extends to the dermis. The follicle is lined by an inner and outer sheath that

protects and molds the growing hair and ends just before the opening of sebaceous gland. The hair shaft is the part of the hair that is made up of three layers of keratin. The inner layer is also called as medulla. Depending on type of hair, the medulla is not always present. The middle layer is called the cortex which makes most of the hair shaft. The outer layer is also called as cuticle, which is formed by tightly packed scales in an overlapping structure that resemble roof shingles.

Hair type is primarily based on hair curl pattern. The amount of curl in the hair is determined by hair follicle. Hair type is determined by genetics. Andre walker, known for decades as Oprah Winfrey's stylist, is credited with devising a system that classifies hair according to one of four curl patterns: Type 1-Straight, Type 2-Wavy, Type 3-Curly, Type 4-Coily.

Hair growth cycle consists of 3 stages (4) i.e., Anagen phase- The anagen phase is the growth phase of the hair. Catagen phase – The catagen phase is a transitional stage and 3% of all hairs are in this phase at any given time and the hair stops growing and becomes detached from the base of the follicle. Telogen phase- The telogen phase is the resting phase and during this phase the hair does not grow but stays attached to the follicle.

HERBAL COSMETICS USED FOR HAIR

Hair cosmetics are an important tool that helps to increase patient's adherence to alopecia and scalp treatments. Knowledge of hair cosmetics and esthetic procedures as well as of the hair shaft structure and physical behavior is indeed relevant in today's medical practice. (54) Cosmetics are substances used to enhance the appearance or odor of the mortal body. Cosmetics include skin care creams, poultices, maquillages, scents, powders and toe nail polish, eye and facial makeup, colored contact lenses, hair colors, hair sprays and gels, deodorants, baby products, bath canvases, flannel, and numerous other types of products. (55) Herbal cosmetics are prepared by the association of active bioactive constituents or medicinal.

A. HAIR OIL

Hair oil are hair care products. Hair care products are defined as the formulations which are used for the purpose of cleansing, modifying, the hair texture, providing nourishment to the hair and maintaining the healthy appearance of hair. (5) Hair oil is hair care formulation applied to the hair for the treatment of hair disorder such as baldness, graying of hair, hair

fall, dry hair and also helps in providing nourishment to hair. (6) Herbal cosmetics are high in demand due to increasing interest of mankind towards them also herbal cosmetics are more effective with negligible side effects and ingredients are easily available. (7) Herbal hair oil is an essential part of herbal cosmetics. Herbal hair oil is more preferred and used in many ailments of hair. They not only promote hair growth but also provide necessary moisture to the scalp rendering in beautiful hair. (8) Herbal oil which contain herbal drugs are known as hair tonic (9) Herbal hair oil provide several essential nutrients which are important to maintain the normal function of sebaceous gland and promote natural growth of hair. (10) These are one of the most well recognized products for the treatment of hair. (11) The use of hair oil is increasing every day in line with the improvement in standard of living of people to give natural flavors and colors to hair oil the herbal essences and perfumed are added.

Different Types of Herbal Hair Oil available in Market

Table 1: Chemical Properties & Effects of medicinal herbs in hair

Hair Oil	Biological Source	Chemical Composition	Effect on Hair
Amla hair oil	<i>Emblca officinalis</i>	Vitamin C (ascorbic acid), ellagic acid, chebulinic acid, gallic acid, chebulagic acid, quercetin, leutolin	Antifungal effect, Graying of hair, Anti- microbial (12, 13,14,15)
Coconut hair oil	<i>Coccus nucifera</i>	Fatty acids (myristic acid, monolaurin, capric acid, lauric acid) (16), phenolic acids and antioxidants (tocopherol) (17)	Saponification, Antibacterial activity, Antifungal activity, Lubricants, Preventing protein loss (18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23)
Almond hair oil	<i>Prunus amygdalus</i>	Monosaturated fatty acid, poly unsaturated fatty acid (24), oleic acid, linoleic acid, stearic acid, palmitic acid. (25)	Protection against ultraviolet (UV) damage, Emollient, Elasticity, Protein Loss (26, 27, 28)
Castor Hair Oil	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Glycerides of isoricinoleic acid, ricin oleic, dihydroxystearic acid, stearic acid, (25) eicosanoid acid, linoleic acid, palmitic, and linoleic acid.	Moisturizing effect, Nourishing effect, Germicidal and fungicidal effect, In androgenetic alopecia (29, 30,31)
Argan Hair Oil	<i>Argania spinose</i>	Monosaturated (80%), saturated (20%) fatty acids (27), sterols, polyphenols,	Sebostatic, Moisturizing effect (33)

		tocopherols, triterpene alcohols, squalene, palmitic, stearic, linolenic, and linoleic acid. (32)	
Olive Hair Oil	Oleo europoea	Arachin, linolein, palmitin, olein (34), sterols, carotenoids, triterpenic oils, and phenolic compounds. The virgin olive oil is a rich source of antioxidants that contains flavonoids, lignans, and secoiridoids. (35)	Emollient effect, Photo protection, Antifungal effect, In psoriasis (36, 37)
Fenugreek Hair Oil	Trigonella foenum graecum L	Diosgenin is a steroid sapogenin which is found in fenugreek. Other sapogenins found in yamogenin, gitogenin, tigogenin, and neotigogens. It also contains alkaloids such as trigonelline, gentianine, and carpine compounds. (40)	Androgenetic alopecia, Anti-fungal effect, Bactericidal activity, Emollient (41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46)
Sesame Hair Oil	Sesamum indicum	Sesame oil contains Palmitic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid, gadoleic acid, behenic acid, stearic acid, and aracidic acid. It contains high amounts of sesamol, sesaminol, sesamin. (27) Sesamol provides stability to the oil. (25) It also contains sesame lignans. (47)	Anti-inflammatory properties, Antioxidant effect, UV-induced damage, Moisturizing agent (47, 48, 49)
Mustard Hair Oil	Brassica nigra	Arachidic, behenic, linoleic, oleic, palmitic, erucic, lignoceric, and myristic acid. (50). It also consists of carotenoids, tocopherol, and sinigrin. (51)	Anti-oxidant property, sunscreen, Antifungal (51, 52, 53)

B. SHAMPOO

Shampoos are not only scalp cleaners, but indubitably act as preventing the hair shaft damage. Many scalp diseases are also treated by active ingredients that are added to the shampoo's formulations. It is desirable that whatever may be the disease or condition (dermatitis, seborrhea, alopecia, psoriasis), the hair strands are kept aesthetically presentable, preserving its softness, combability and shine while treating the scalp. (56) Shampoos are usually perceived as products that do not damage hair. However, there is evidence indicating these products may contribute to hair damage through abrasive or erosive actions. They may result in the degradation of the non- Keratinous components of the endocuticle and CMC.

Even below the maximum amount legally allowed, shampoos may also contain preservatives, such as quaternium-15, imidazolidinyl urea, and diazolidinyl urea, with antimicrobial effect that function through the release of trace amounts of formaldehyde, a potential sensitizer as referred previously and an inhalation carcinogenic (57). Different types of herbal shampoos used in market are:

- a. Anti – Hair fall shampoo with Amla and Neem.
- b. Moisturizing shampoo with Aloe Vera and Wheat germ
- c. Anti- Dandruff Shampoo with Hibiscus and Vetiver
- d. Volumizing Shampoo with Fenugreek and Shikakai

All shampoos have certain basic ingredients like:

1. Anionic- It provides a lot of the lather and detergency in the shampoo. They have negatively charged functional group, e.g. sodium lauryl sulphate, sodium laureth sulfate and ammonium laureth sulfate.
2. Cationic- They are devoid of detergent or foaming properties, but are excellent hair conditioners. They have positively charged functional group. Cationic surfactants are composed of a polar or non-polar part, e.g. long chain amino esters, ammonioesters.
3. Amphoteric- These surfactants are used as cosurfactants in shampoo to stabilize micelles formation, helping improve lather stability and viscosity building. It is also used to decrease the irritancy of shampoo formulations, e.g. betaines, sultaines, imidazolinium derivatives.

4. Foaming agent- It facilitate the formation of a foam, or enhance its colloidal stability. Most common foaming agents are used in shampoos are sodium laureth sulphate (SLES), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS).

5. Additives- These are used to increase the shampoo viscosity; however, overdose of these thickeners may cause negative hair feel, e.g. parabens, glycol, sulfates, and formaldehyde etc.

C. CONDITIONERS

Conditioners reduce friction, detangle the hair, minimize frizz and improve combability, restore hydrophobicity, enhance shine, smoothness, and manageability. Conditioners act by neutralizing the electrical negative charge of the hair fiber by adding positive charges and by lubricating the cuticle that reduces fiber hydrophilicity. They contain anti- static and lubricating substances that are divided into 5 main groups: Polymers, oils, waxes, hydrolyzed amino acids and cationic molecules. (58) Conditioners fulfill the need for hair shaft protection and are agents either incorporated into shampoos or used after cleansing, on slightly damp hair. After a shampoo wash, the cuticles get slightly lifted, and the hair develops a negative charge causing the hair to repel each other and appear rough and uncombed. Conditioners flatten the cuticles and seal the gaps that could expose the important cortex to environmental damage. Conditioning agents incorporated into shampoos (labeled as conditioning shampoos/dry hair shampoos/hair fall shampoos) include mineral oils, vegetables oils, fatty alcohols/ esters, humectants, hydrolyzed animal proteins, glycerin, stearylalkonium chloride, propylene glycol, silicones (dimethicone, simethicone), and natural products like bees honey an emulsion of proteins sugars and lipids), vinegar, wheat germ oil, panthenol, collagen, and placenta. Silicones have become very popular as they provide good 'slip' and luster, and retain moisture in the hair, but silicone oil is hydrophobic and it does not get absorbed onto the hair very easily. (59).

Functions of the conditioners

1. Improve combability
2. Mimetize the hair natural lipid outer layer: 18- MEA
3. Restore hydrophobicity
4. Seal the cuticle

5. Avoid or minimize frizz, friction: Neutralize the negative charged net
6. Enhance shine, smoothness, and manageability.

D. HERBAL HAIR DYES

There are many types of hair dyes classified according to the penetration of the dye to the surface or to deep parts of the hair shaft, e.g. Demi permanent and permanent dyes. It is a practice of changing the hair color. There are many herbal plants used for hair coloring. Some herbs are available worldwide, but some are traditionally planted and found only in Thailand or neighboring countries. Some herbal plants used are – Henna, Reetha, Coffee, Clove, Walnut, Bhringraj, etc. (60) The main difference between the dyes is their capacity to reach the cortex and stay there in a permanent way or to not reach the cortex and stay shallow on the cuticle surface and be washable after about 10-15 shampoos. Those are the demi-permanent dyes. To overcome the cuticle and reach the cortex, the product must have an alkaline pH able to open the scales. Most of the times the permanent dyes use ammonia to increase the Ph. Some products are referred to be ammonia-free but instead, they carry ethanolamine with the purpose. Both substances remove the natural cuticle lipid, the 18-metil eicosanoic acid, which confers hydrophobicity to the fiber. The use of permanent dyes may cause damage by removing the 18 MEA and making the hair hydrophilic. (58)

ADVANTAGES OF HERBAL HAIR DYES

1. Herbal dyes are not harmful to environmental or consumer because of its natural origin
2. Herbal dyes gives a natural shade and help to achieve soft, soothing, look.
3. No chemical reaction involved during dye preparation.
4. Herbal dyes will not cause harm or health problems.
5. Herbal dyes having no disposal problem. (60)

DISADVANTAGES OF HERBAL HAIR DYES

1. Herbal hair dyes are difficult to standardize or blend.
2. Herbal hair dyes are difficult to produce because of its availability of raw material.

3. Herbal dye preparation is a lengthy dyeing preparation.
4. Herbal dyes having inadequate degree of fixation.
5. Natural herbal dyes having poor reproducibility of shade. (60)

APPLICATIONS

1. Increase moisture, luster, and shine.
2. Preventing hair loss,
3. Reduce the amount of water absorbed by the hair shaft,
4. Softer and smoother

HERBAL MEDICINES FOR HAIR CARE TREATMENTS

1. Amla: Biological source: Dried fruits of *Phyllanthus emblica*, Family: Phyllanthaceae, it is deciduous tree widely found in India at the height of 350m. It is often cultivated at commercial level in Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Rajasthan, and Maharashtra. Amla contains 5-6 % of tannins such as gallic acid, ellagic acid and phyllembelin. Use: Amla is a natural immunity booster that also helps to maintain hair health. It is loaded with essential fatty acids, which effectively strengthen hair follicles, thus making your hair strong and shiny. It also raises the levels of sebum production, which can help get rid of dandruff, scalp itchiness and dandruff.

2. Bhringraj: Biological source: *Eclipta prostrata*, Family: Asteraceae, it is an annual or perennial plant found in moist places throughout India, ascending to 600 fts. Bhringraj contains coumestans (ecalbasaponins). Use: This medicine for hair growth is a solution to every hair problem. Bhringraj is known for promoting hair regrowth and stops hair loss completely. It is one of the main constituents for herbal preparations used in the management of hair loss due to its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anti- allergic properties.

3. Shikakai: Biological source: *Senegalia ruguta*, Family: Fabaceae, it is a shrub widely used in plains of central and south India. Shikakai literally means fruit of hairs. It is an excellent natural hair cleanser and astringent and acts as detangle. Use: It is loaded with antioxidants and vitamins that promote hair regrowth. Shikakai is used in many shampoos

and conditions for its rich content of saponins. Here are some examples of how shikakai can be used for hair care: Take 20 tablespoons of shikakai, 10 teaspoons Reetha, 5 teaspoons Tulsi and Neem powder. Mix all the ingredients, whenever required take 1-2 teaspoons of powder and add some water to make paste. Apply on wet hair and scalp and massage gently. After this wash your hair with cool tap water.

4.Brahmi: Biological source: *Bacopa monnieri*, Family: Plantaginaceae, it is herbaceous creeping herb growing at the bank of river. In India, Brahmi is found in wet damp and marshy places of north India. Brahmi contains essential oils, sterols, flavanols, glycoside and triterpenoid saponins. Use: Brahmi is considered the best herb for hair regrowth as it effectively activates the protein in the body. One can attain long, beautiful, healthy hair if they regularly use Brahmi oil on their scalp. Brahmi also helps in heal split ends and prevent more from occurring. It acts as a natural conditioner. The herb also treats bald patches efficiently in people. It also contains alkaloids thought to activate proteins responsible for hair growth.

5.Methi Seeds: Biological source: *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, Family: Fabaceae, Use: also known as fenugreek, are rich in vitamin and folic acid that promote hair growth. It also has nicotinic acid; which controls hair fall problems. These seeds accelerate hair growth by nourishing the scalp. It also rich in potassium which prevents against graying hair. One can mix methi seeds with coconut oil and then apply it to their scalp to grow strong hair. Here are some tips how to used methi seeds for hair care: Take 25 grams of soaked methi seeds, 25 grams of curd, lemon juice, honey, and water, blend all the ingredients together into fine paste. Apply this hair pack all over your hair, wash this pack with a mild shampoo after 40-45 minutes.

6.Aloe Vera Gel: Biological source: *Aloe vera*, Family: Aphodelaceae, Use: The gel helps restore the scalp natural pH balance, promoting hair growth. This herbal medicine for hair growth is a great way to keep the hair moisturized and hydrated. Aloe Vera gel prevents excessive hair fall by preventing dry and itchy scalp. It also strengthens and repairs hair strands. The gel can be mixed with other ayurvedic herbs and applied as a paste to witness maximum results.

7. Ginseng: Biological source: Genus *Panax*, Family: *Araliaceae*, Use: Ginseng is an age-old natural remedy for my conditions, including hair loss. It contains saponins, which are believed to encourage hair growth by inhibiting 5 α reductase. This is an enzyme related to hair loss in men. Ginseng improves blood circulation to the scalp, ensuring that hair follicles have an adequate supply of oxygen and nutrients. Improved scalp circulation nourishes and revitalizes hair follicles, promoting optimal hair growth and strength.

8. Hibiscus Flower: Biological source: Genus *Hibiscus*, Family: *Malvaceae*, Use: Hibiscus contains high vitamin C and A, iron and has anti-inflammatory properties. Making herbal hair masks with hibiscus flower paste or hibiscus infused oil can take care of hair loss, dandruff, improves hair shine, condition's hair and promote hair regrowth (length and thickness). This herb has been used in traditional medicine for centuries to treat hair loss and thinning hair. It is also safe and simple to use, making it popular choice for natural hair care products.

RECENT ADVANCEMENTS IN HERBAL HAIR COSMETICS

Shah et al., 2018 prepared and evaluated polyherbal hair oil. This study aimed at reviewing the importance of polyherbal hair oil for the treatment of common hair problems such as baldness, alopecia, hair fall, gray hair, dryness, and most common dandruff. They used various herbal ingredients in the formulation are: Amla, Almond, Garlic, Curry leaves, Coconut oil, Mehndi powder, Neem, Castor oil provide essential nutrients such as vitamins, antioxidant, protein, terpenoids, and many essential oils to maintain normal function of sebaceous gland. The formulated oil was evaluated for its organoleptic properties, acid value, saponification value, viscosity, pH etc. Result findings showed that they are within the limits and since all the ingredients added have many advantages, this oil will help in maintaining good growth of hair, turning grey hair to black, protects from dandruff and results in lustrous looking hair.

Havelikar et al., 2023 prepared herbal plants based herbal hair dye. This research was aimed at the preparation of herbal hair dye and the evaluation of its various parameters as organoleptic, physico-chemical, phytoconstituents, patch test, and stability testing for its efficacy and shelf life. The composition of organic hair dye consisting of *Lawsonia inermis*, *Emblica officinalis*, *Ocimum sanctum*, *Trigonella foenum*, *Citrus aurantium* and *Lobhhasma*. The main aim of the formulation and evaluation of herbal hair dye was to minimize the side

effects of synthetic and semisynthetic hair dye. In this study, they discovered that the herbal hair pack has beneficial qualities, it nourishes the scalp and hair skin. It is a notable attempt to create an herbal hair pack including the benefits of plant powders that were wonderful for hair care.

Darade et al., 2023 formulate and evaluate herbal hair oil. This article emphasizes the importance of herbal hair oil for the healthy life of hairs. This article involves the objectives of herbal hair oil, which includes herbal goodness of hair, manage frizzy hair etc. The commonly used ingredients were coconut oil, jasmine, hibiscus, almond oil. The natural extract and ingredients chosen for the method of hair oil had been suggested to have hair thickening and hair fall manipulate homes which used together licited a synergistic effect in selling healthy and vivid hair increase. This natural hair oil formulation has sizeable first class.

Pal et al., 2018 synthesis and evaluation of herbal based hair dye. This research was aimed at the preparation of herbal hair dye and the evaluation of its various parameters as rheological aspects, patch test, stability testing and phytoconstituents for its efficacy and shelf life. This hair formulation provides vital nourishment to the skin. Frequent use of their pack leads to manageable, frizz free colored hair. In this research, they found effective properties of the herbal hair pack.

Bakr et al., 2019 prepared polyherbal conditioning and antioxidant shampoo” there study aimed at the formulation of a natural foaming agent, in addition to having conditioning, antioxidant, and antimicrobial effects. The shampoo formulated with Spina- Christi, G. glabra and S. Babylonia etc. The antimicrobial activity of the plant extract was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method and compared with the optimized shampoo formulation against the following pathogenic microorganism. Therefore, there product can help to promote hair healthy, providing satisfaction with few side effects. The formulated polyherbal shampoo is chemical free, extra nourishing shampoo with excellent conditioning, cleansing, and antimicrobial effects.

Bare et al., 2023 formulation and evaluation of herbal hair conditioner. there main purpose is to reduce friction between hairs, making brushing and combing easier. The various ingredients are used in their formulation are fenugreek, hibiscus flowers, and curry leaves. It was analyzed by various evaluation parameters like pH test, dirt dispersion test, viscosity, wetting time etc. They concluded that hair exhibits excellent properties and applied to hair

after washing provide smooth hair, improve shine and repair damaged, and weathered hair also that conditioners are free of chemical ingredients and therefore safe to use on all scalp types.

Snehal et al., 2021 a bucolic remedy of formulation and evaluation of polyherbal hair oil, there study aimed to formulate polyherbal hair oil using various efficient herbs like coccus nucifera(oil), Ricinus communis(oil), nigella seeds(flowers), and Cinnamomum camphor in form of oil using boiling method, their evaluation of hair oil carries out various parameters such as acid value, saponification value, specific gravity, and irritation test. Therefore, they concluded that formulated oil boosts hair growth, decrease hair falls and gives lustrous or shiny hairs as compared to market formulations.

Maurya et al., 2022 development and characterization of herbal anti-dandruff hair oil” the main aim of their learning involves preparation and evaluation of herbal hair oil by using fresh parts of a variety of plants, few of these herbs are aloe vera pulp, Tulsi, guava leaves, coconut oil, methi, it bestows numerous essential nutrients to maintain normal function of sebaceous gland and promotes hair growth. In conclusion, oil is beneficial to prevent hair from damage and loss caused by pollution and dull hair and also provides an alternative source from hazardous chemicals.

Tiwari et al., 2021 assessment of nutraceutical potential of herbs for promoting hair growth. Hair loss is a relatively common occurrence that causes concern in people of all ages, in most of the cases, hair loss is permanent so it is necessary to improve hair development and prevent hair loss. Various herbs are collected and dried (murraya koenigii, hibiscus rosa-sinesis linn, nigella sativa) were combined with 60% cocas nucifera oil, various parameters were determined. As a result, herbal hair oil was odorless and reddish brown in appearance and exhibited good pH and acceptable viscosity and stable at room temperature so it is clear that the herbal plant may be preferable option for future formulations.

Nikam et al., 2019 formulate and evaluate herbal shampoo. The hair care herbal shampoo powder has been prepared using some of the traditional medicines like bahera, amla, neem, Tulsi, Shikakai and Brahmi were evaluated for organoleptic, powder characteristics, foam test and physical evaluation. The study showed that the active ingredients of these drugs when incorporated in shampoo gives more stable products with good aesthetic appeal, they conclude that the powdered herbal shampoo formula reduces swelling, reduces side effects, and improves conditioning.

CONCLUSION

The current applications of herbs in hair cosmetics have shown promising results, offering natural alternatives for hair care. Herbs like aloe vera, bhringraj, shikakai, brahmi and amla have been utilized for their moisturizing, nourishing, and soothing properties in various hair products. They contribute to scalp health, hair growth stimulation, and overall hair vitality. Additionally, herbs are increasingly incorporated into formulations targeting specific hair concerns such as dandruff, hair loss, and scalp irritation. As consumers seek safer and more sustainable options, the use of herbs in hair cosmetics continues to gain traction as a viable and effective solution.

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